

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PROVIDING PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP TO PERSONS IN DANGEROUS AND EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

**Karshi State University independent researcher
Shomurodov Ibrokhim Uzbekistan, Karshi
Email: ibrohimshomurodov93@gmail.com**

Annotation: The article provides information about the types of extreme situations of a person, analyzed them from a psychological point of view, and highlighted the socio-psychological features of providing psychological assistance to a person in such a situation.

Key words: Stress, apathy, fear, anxiety, anger.

Аннотация: В статье приведены сведения о видах экстремальных ситуаций человека, проанализированы их с психологической точки зрения, выделены социально-психологические особенности оказания психологической помощи человеку, находящемуся в такой ситуации.

Ключевые слова: Стресс, апатия, страх, тревога, гнев.

A person who falls into an extreme state can be called a special psychological state. This state can be called a high reflex effect of stress in medicine and psychology.

In an extreme case, a person may fall into a state of unconsciousness, anxiety, anger, fear, high mobility is observed, but it does not last for a long time.

Symptoms pass quickly (from a few hours to a few days).

There is a close relationship between stress and its symptoms (a few minutes)

A person who has experienced such an event needs the help of a specialist, that is, a psychologist or a doctor.

In extreme situations, the main problem is that the casual (psychologist-specific) aid manual is divided into two blocks, so that the victim can be helped again by a lay person who is not a specialist.

The first part is about how to help the victim and how to help yourself.

Second, rapid psychological support in response to stress. The following rules should be taken into account in psychological support.

Ways to help in the following cases: fear, anxiety, crying, temptation, apathy, guilt, anger, uncontrollable trembling state of movement.

It is important to think about your own safety because the person who is grieving cannot control their actions, so be careful. People trying to commit suicide took the person they wanted to help with them).

Schedule medical care. The victim has physical injuries, fractures, and the condition of the heart. If necessary, it is necessary to call an ambulance, for some reason, medical help may not be provided immediately. In such a situation, your action should be as follows. Notify the victim that help is coming.

Advise him what to do in such a situation will be convenient for him: how to save energy, not to take deep breaths, breathe slowly through the nose, this will give an opportunity to save oxygen in the body, even to save oxygen from the environment. Prohibit the victim from trying to save himself.

When you are around a person who has suffered psychological trauma due to extreme factors (during a terrorist attack, accident, loss of a loved one, receiving terrible news, physical or sexual violence, etc.), make sure that the victim's condition does not surprise you, scare you, or otherwise should not affect his state, actions, excitement, is a normal reflection of an unusual situation.

If you feel that you can't help, if you don't like it, it's better not to communicate with him, why? feels and your sincere but insecure effort may end in failure, it is better to find someone else to help.

Help in fear. Do not leave the victim alone because fear is worse in isolation. Talk about what the person is afraid of. If the victim talks about what they are afraid of, talk about it. Never think about it, tell the victim that it's not true, that it's stupid. Offer the victim several breathing exercises.

1. Put your hands on your stomach: breathe slowly through your nose and chest, then your stomach will be filled with air. Breath is held for 1-2 seconds and exhaled. This exercise is repeated 3-4 times.

2. Take a deep breath. Breath is held for 1-2 seconds. Start exhaling halfway through, stop for 1-2 seconds and continue exhaling. Try to exhale forcefully. If the victim is struggling, breathe together, this will help him calm down and make him feel that you are there.

If the victim is a child, talk about what he is afraid of and then play with him, and draw pictures, make figures and so on.

Try to provide the victim with some work

Support for anxiety.

He should talk to the victim and find out what worries him. In doing so, the person will find out what exactly worries him.

A person is worried if he does not have accurate information about the phenomenon. Engage the victim in mental work such as writing, reading, etc.

"Physical work and housework are a good sedative. Running and exercising are beneficial if conditions allow.

Assistance provided in Yigi. Crying is a good way to release inner tension. It is good not to interrupt when a crying person is crying, but it is also not good not to stand next to a crying person and comfort him. What should the aid consist of?

You can express your attitude not by words but by your actions. You can sit next to him, take him in your arms, pat his head, pat his shoulder, by this you can show that you sympathize with him. You can hold his hand, sometimes a pressed hand is better than a hundred words.

Convulsion. Convulsion is a condition that requires immediate cessation. Why, in this case, strong physical and psychological effort is spent. The victim can be helped as follows.

Help in memory loss (apathy). In the state of apathy, together with the lack of strength, in the state of falling into the void, if the person is not supported and strengthened, he will fall into a state of depression. In this case, the following assistance is required.

Talk to the victim, ask him a few simple questions - what is your name, how do you feel, are you eating?

Take the victim to a resting place. Make sure it fits properly (shoes must be removed). Take his hand and put your hand on his forehead.

Create conditions for him to sleep and rest.

If there are no conditions for rest (on the street, in public transport, in a hospital, in an apartment), have more conversations with the victim, involve him in joint activities (traveling, going for coffee, tea, helping others together).

Help with guilt or guilt. If you have someone struggling with guilt, encourage them to see a professional. In such a situation, he needs the help of a specialist psychologist, doctor, psychotherapist.

Talk, try to put him to bed. Confirm that you hear him and understand him (nodding "yes", "right" etc.). Do not judge his actions, even if he seems guilty to you, accept him as he is, do not tell him that you are not guilty, that this situation happens to everyone. Do not talk about your experience, do not ask questions, just listen.

Help with the inability to control physical movement. Inability to control physical movement occurs during an inability to control movement in an acute reaction to stress . It can be dangerous for others and for oneself. In this case, try to physically

stop the victim. Before trying to help, try to limit your possibilities. Psychological help is shown only if the victim can respond to his situation.

REFERENCES:

- 1.Фрейд З. Психология бессознательного: Сборник. Произведниэ /Сост.и науч. ред. М. Т. Ярошевского.-М.: Просвешениэ, 1990.-448 с.
- 2.Чудновский В.Э. Индивидуальный стиль деятельности школьников// Сов. пед-ка, 1989. - № 9.-С.69-75.
- 3.Шихирев П.Н. Социальная установка как предмет социально-психологического исследования // Психологическиэ проблемы социальной концепции поведения. М.: 1976.-С.114-144.
- 4.Стреляу Я. Рол темперамента в психологическом развитии.-М.: 1983. - 98 с.
- 5.Лупян Я.А. Бареры общения, конфликты, стресс. – Минск: Вишейшая школа, 1986. – 206с.
- 6.Магомед-Эминов М.Ш. Трансформация личности. –М.: Психоаналитическая Ассоциация, 1998.-496 с.
- 7.Чудновский В.Э. Индивидуальный стиль деятельности школьников// Сов. пед-ка, 1989. - № 9.-С.69-75.
- 8.Теплов Б.М. Проблемы индивидуальных различий – М.: 1961. - 536 с.